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NEWS

Visual Astronomy Display: September 2014

Katie Frey Updated on August 24, 2022 [Leave a Comment](#)

Visual Astronomy Display for September 2014

Highlights...

- The Rosetta mission is still going strong! One video illustrates the key dates of the upcoming sequence of **maneuvers that will bring Rosetta even closer to comet 67P**;
- Historic **footage from Voyager 2's 1989 flyby of Triton**, a moon of Neptune, has been restored, color corrected, and recently released, providing the best-ever global color map of this strange moon;
- A NASA sounding rocket has confirmed that **the solar system is inside an ancient supernova remnant**;
- Minute Physics explains **why stars sometimes appear to have spokes or points**, and aren't just simple dots of light as seen from Earth; and
- Scientists have recently gathered strong evidence that might explain **what makes the sun's outer atmosphere so hot** compared with its surface.

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#RosettaAreWeThereYet – Fabulous fables and tales of tails

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Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

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